

Composition and Stability of Streptomycin Complexes with Ni(II) & Co(II)

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Conductometric and pH-metric studies have shown 1 : 1 complexation of streptomycin with Ni(II) and Co(II). The stability constant (log K) and the free energy of formation (ΔF) of these complexes at 30° and at a constant ionic strength (0.1M NaClO₄) have been determined.

IN continuation of our previous work¹, we have carried out the physico-chemical investigations of Ni(II) and Co(II) complexes with streptomycin. The complexation of these metals with streptomycin was first reported by Foye and Lange². In the present investigation, the studies have been extended to the evaluation of the composition and determination of the stability constant (log K) and the free energy of formation (ΔF) of these complexes using conductometric and pH-metric titration techniques.

Material and Methods

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared and standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate. Streptomycin perchlorate (SMPC) was prepared from B.P. grade streptomycin sulphate as in the previous work¹. All the solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

An 'ELICO' model L-10 pH-meter (accuracy 0.05) with glass and calomel electrodes was used for pH-metric titrations. Conductometric titrations were performed using 'Toshniwal' conductivity bridge and a dip type cell (cell constant 0.46). Titrations were performed using a microburette calibrated up to 0.01 ml.

Composition of the complexes :

This was evaluated by conductometric titrations at 20° using streptomycin sulphate solution. 5 ml of 0.05M streptomycin sulphate were diluted to 200 ml with water. The pH of the solution was maintained at 8.0 by adding sodium hydroxide

solution. Conductivity was measured after each 0.5 ml addition of 0.05M metal salt solution. After making the necessary volume correction, the titration results are plotted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Conductometric Titration Curves

Stability constants :

Potentiometric pH-titrations were performed for the determination of the stability constants. Titration of the ligand was carried out in the presence and absence of metal ions.

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Following sets of titrations were performed :

- A. 5 ml 0.025 *M* SMPC + 5 ml *M* NaClO₄
 + 1 ml 0.02 *M* HClO₄ + 39.0 ml water.
- B. 5 ml 0.025 *M* SMPC + 5 ml *M* NaClO₄
 + 1 ml 0.02 *M* HClO₄ + 2.5 ml 0.025 *M* Ni(ClO₄)₂
 + 36.5 ml water.
- C. 5 ml 0.025 *M* SMPC + 5 ml *M* NaClO₄
 + 1 ml 0.02 *M* HClO₄ + 2.5 ml 0.025 *M* Co(ClO₄)₂
 + 36.5 ml water.

Thus the total volume in each case was 50 ml and the metal to ligand ratio was 1 : 2 in mixtures A and B. Ionic strength was maintained constant at 0.1 *M* NaClO₄. The titration curves of these mixtures against 0.5 *M* sodium hydroxide solution are plotted in Fig. 2.

Results and Discussion

Conductometric titration curves (Fig. 1, curves A and B) show only one break at one mole of metal ion added per mole of ligand which clearly indicates that Ni(II) and Co(II) form 1 : 1 complex with streptomycin.

pH-metric titration curves (Fig. 2) showed considerable lowering of the buffer region in the metal titration curves with respect to the ligand titration curve indicating liberation of protons as a result of interaction between the metal and the ligand molecules. Both the curves A and B suffered a break at 2 mole of base per mole ligand which corresponds to the formation of 1 : 1 complexes and the neutralisation of the excess ligand. The hydrolysis of the

Fig. 2. Titration of SMPC against NaOH in the absence and presence of ● Cobalt and ○ Nickel. Curve A : Ligand titration curve common for both experiments.

metal ions is accompanied by the liberation of protons, and as such a displacement of metal titration curve is possible even in the absence of any reaction with the reagent. In the present study however, no precipitate was observed below pH 9.0 and hence all the calculations were done below this pH range.

\bar{n} and pA^- values were determined from these curves in the usual manner following the Bjerrum method³ as modified by Calvin and Melchior⁴. The concentration of anion (A^-), of the chelating agent, was calculated from the knowledge of the acid dissociation constant¹ of SMPC and the pH of the solution.

Values of pA^- were plotted against \bar{n} . The formation curves (Fig. 3), thus obtained are of the order of 1. This is in conformity to the 1 : 1 complexation

Fig. 3. Formation curves of SMPC complexes with ● Co(II) and ○ Ni(II).

of streptomycin with the metals under study. The approximate values of the stability constants ($\log K$) was directly read from these curves at $\bar{n} = 0.5$. These values were further modified by the Bjerrum method of successive approximation⁵.

Free energy of formation of these complexes at 30° were calculated from the knowledge of the stability constants using the following equation.

$$\Delta F = -2.303 RT \log K.$$

The results are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANT OF STREPTOMYCIN COMPLEXES WITH Ni(II) AND Co(II)

Metal ion	$\log K$	ΔF
Ni(II)	2.09	-2.79 Kcals per mole
Co(II)	2.17	-3.05 Kcals per mole

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